

GRAMMATICAL RULES OF PRINCIPLES OF ENGLISH TO DARI TRANSLATION

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Abstract: In this article, we will explore the key grammatical rules and principles that should be followed when translating from English to Dari, and analyze the challenges and strategies involved in this process.

Key Words: Dari, English, Rules, Translation, Principles, Grammatical.

INGLIZ TILIDAN DARI TILIGA TARJIMA TAMOYILLARINING GRAMMATIK QOIDALARI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz ingliz tilidan dari tiliga tarjima qilishda rioya qilinishi kerak bo‘lgan asosiy grammatik qoidalar va tamoyillarni o‘rganamiz va bu jarayonda ishtirok etadigan qiyinchiliklar va strategiyalarni tahlil qilamiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: Dari, Ingliz tili, Qoidalar, Tarjima, Prinsiplar, Grammatik.

INTRODUCTION

Observing grammatical rules and techniques is the first step to start working in the field of principles of English to Dari translation. These grammatical rules are Recent research has shown the cultural component of many lexical units For instance, points out that “the meaning of words provides the best evidence for the reality of cultures as ways of speaking, thinking and living.” Official documents are essential tools in the functioning of any society¹. They serve as a means of communication, record-keeping, and verification of information. Official documents can take many forms, including government-issued identification cards, birth certificates, marriage licenses, passports, and academic transcripts. These documents are considered to be authoritative and legally binding, and they play a crucial role in various aspects of our lives².

¹. Inchaurrealde, C. (2003). “Marked communication and cultural knowledge in lexis”, in C. Zelinsky- Wibbelt (ed.) Text, Context, Concepts. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter: 179-196.

². Wierzbicka, A. (2008). “A conceptual basis for intercultural pragmatics and world-wide understanding”, in M. Pütz and J. Neff-van Aertselaer (eds.) Developing Contrastive Pragmatics. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter: 3-45.

Translation is the process of converting text from one language to another while maintaining the original meaning and intent of the content. When translating from English to Dari, it is important to adhere to the grammatical rules and principles of both languages in order to produce an accurate and coherent translation. In this article, we will explore the key grammatical rules and principles that should be followed when translating from English to Dari, and analyze the challenges and strategies involved in this process. One of the fundamental principles of translation is to ensure that the meaning of the original text is preserved in the translated version. This requires a deep understanding of both languages and their grammatical structures. In English, sentences are typically structured in a subject-verb-object format, while Dari follows a subject-object-verb format. This difference in sentence structure can pose a challenge for translators, as they must rearrange the words in the sentence to maintain the correct order in the target language. Another important aspect of translation is the use of tense and verb conjugation. English has a complex system of verb tenses, including past, present, and future, as well as various forms of the verb depending on the subject. Dari, on the other hand, has a simpler system of verb conjugation, with fewer tenses and forms. Translators must be careful to match the tense and form of the verb in the target language to that of the original text in order to convey the correct meaning. Pronouns are another key element of grammar that must be considered when translating from English to Dari. English has a variety of pronouns, including personal, possessive, and reflexive pronouns, which must be translated accurately into Dari. In Dari, pronouns are inflected to indicate the subject, object, or possessive form, which can be challenging for translators to navigate.

In addition to these grammatical considerations, translators must also be mindful of cultural nuances and idiomatic expressions that may not have direct equivalents in the target language. This requires a deep understanding of the cultural context of both languages in order to accurately convey the intended meaning of the original text. Principles of verb and subject translation and their matching The verb and the subject must match each other in terms of the person. There are two modes; First, if the subject is animate, the verb becomes plural or singular according to it. For example: His parents came/Ali came.

مثلاً: پدر و مادرش آمدند/ علی آمد.

If the verb is not animate, having or not matching the subject with the verb is both correct. For example, the sentences "the flowers are placid" and "the flowers are placid" are both correct. If the verb is neither human nor animal, it is correct to have or not match the subject with the verb. For example, the sentences "the flowers are placid" and "the flowers become are placid" are both correct.

مثلاً جمله‌های «گل‌ها پلاسیده شده‌اند» و «گل‌ها پلاسیده شده است» هر دو صحیح هستند.

Principles of translation of prepositions

Prepositions in Dari language are used together with a specific verb or a specific noun. Inappropriate use of prepositions is one of the common mistakes in Dari writing. Usually, when translators translate English to Dari literally, they translate these prepositions incorrectly. In the following, we discuss some of these common mistakes. In the first step, you should read the text you want to translate. The best unit to translate is the sentence. If you want to start from the word, you will definitely face problems in the integration of meaning and concept, and if you use paragraphs, there is a possibility that some sentences will fit, and it will be time-consuming to go back and re-read sentence by sentence. If you encounter a sentence in the source language and start translating only by finding the entity and proposition, you have followed the structural analysis of the sentence; And your sentence may seem logical, but some concepts are conveyed correctly only if the translator has a correct understanding of the culture and environment of the target language and the mood of the writing. This point is called discourse analysis. Therefore, the necessity of reading the text is proven. You will never be able to implement verbal analysis on your translation if you are not aware of the generalities of the subject before starting the translation³.

Not using Arabic words

ندارست	درست
حتی الام کان	تا جایی که می شود
دستورالع مل	دستور کار
بالاخص	به ویژه
حق الزد مه	دستمزد
ممنوع ال کار	ممنوع از کار
تحقیق	پژوهش
ماحصل	دستاورد

³ <https://www.tarjomano.com/%D8%A7%D8%B5%D9%88%D9%84-%D8%AA%D8%B1%D8%AC%D9%85%-D9%87/>

When translating, focus on simplicity and avoid difficult Arabic words as much as possible. If the Arabic word has a Dari equivalent, do not use it and replace it with its Dari equivalent.

نادرست	درست
از تفاوت (different ترجمه تحت الفظی from)	تفاوت با
در تمایل (interested in ترجمه تحت الفظی)	تمایل به
برای علاقه (passion for ترجمه تحت الفظی)	علاقه به
برای چند سال (for several ترجمه تحت الفظی years)	به مدت چند سال

The purpose of translation is to transfer a concept from one language to another, and the translator must do this in the best possible way. Remember that the reader should not solve a puzzle, but should read the text comfortably and move on. The tips that we have presented in the article will help you to a certain extent to have a smoother and more polished translation, but do not forget that the two factors of experience and education are also important. The translation quality is not unaffected⁴. Try to master all the basic rules and techniques of English to Dari translation and become a professional translator.

Dari serves as a unifying force that transcends ethnic and regional differences, fostering a sense of national pride and solidarity. Dari’s status as the official language of Afghanistan is a reflection of its historical, cultural, and linguistic significance in the country. It serves as a symbol of national unity and identity, while also playing a practical role in government, administration, and communication. Dari’s rich literary tradition and widespread use make it a fitting choice for the official language of Afghanistan, embodying the country’s diverse heritage and shared history. One of the primary functions of official documents is to establish and verify one’s identity. Government-issued identification cards, such as driver’s licenses and passports, are used to confirm a person’s identity and citizenship. These documents are required for various activities, such as opening a bank account, applying for a job, or traveling internationally. Without official identification, individuals may face difficulties in

⁴ <https://mrmotarjem.ir/blogs/english-Dari-translation-tips/>

proving who they are and accessing essential services. Official documents also serve as a record of important life events. Birth certificates, marriage licenses, and death certificates are examples of documents that record significant milestones in a person’s life. These documents are used for legal purposes, such as applying for a marriage license or claiming inheritance rights. They also provide valuable information for genealogical research and historical documentation. In addition to personal identification and record-keeping, official documents play a crucial role in maintaining security and order in society. For example, government-issued permits and licenses regulate various activities, such as driving, hunting, and operating a business. These documents ensure that individuals meet certain qualifications and adhere to specific regulations, thereby promoting public safety and accountability.

Furthermore, official documents are used in legal proceedings to establish facts and evidence. Legal documents, such as contracts, deeds, and court orders, are binding agreements that outline rights, responsibilities, and obligations between parties. These documents are crucial in resolving disputes, enforcing laws, and upholding justice. Official documents are essential tools that serve various functions in society. They establish and verify identities, record important life events, maintain security and order, and provide evidence in legal proceedings. Without official documents, individuals would face challenges in proving their identities, accessing services, and upholding their rights. Therefore, it is crucial to recognize the importance of official documents and ensure their accuracy, integrity, and security.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, translating from English to Dari requires a thorough understanding of the grammatical rules and principles of both languages, as well as a keen awareness of cultural nuances and idiomatic expressions. By following these guidelines and employing careful attention to detail, translators can produce accurate and effective translations that convey the intended meaning of the original text.

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